

The Risk Factors Associated with Suicidality in The Perinatal Period: A Systematic Review.

by

Dr. MAHA SADIMA and Dr. LYNSAY MATTHEWS

University of the West of Scotland,
School of Health and Life Sciences,
Hamilton International Technology Park, Stephenson Pl,
Blantyre, Glasgow G72 0LH, United Kingdom

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ABSTRACT:

Background: The perinatal period is a public health priority due to rising maternal mortality, with suicide being a leading cause. Suicidality, including suicidal thoughts, plans, or attempts, has increased in both low- and middle-income countries (LMIC) and high-income countries. Maternal suicidality poses risks to both mothers and children. Research on maternal suicidality is fragmented, with prior reviews focused on the prevalence of suicidality. This systematic review aims to explore the complex factors contributing to perinatal suicidality.

Methods: Following PRISMA guidelines, a systematic review was conducted using the SPiDER framework across PubMed, CINAHL, and Psychology and Behavioral Sciences Collection databases. Studies were included if they presented data on factors contributing to perinatal suicidality and published from 2018 onwards. Data analysis was conducted using narrative synthesis.

Results: This systematic review analysed 18 studies on perinatal suicidality. Women experiencing depression were 2.16 to 16 times more likely to experience suicidality, with postnatal depression posing a higher risk. Anxiety increased the risk by 3 to 4 times, while fetal loss raised it by 2.1 to 5.2 times. Single women faced 1.53 to 5.69 times higher odds of suicidality, and those experiencing intimate partner violence (IPV) had 1.81 to 7.60 times higher odds. Childhood abuse, substance use, and socioeconomic vulnerability also contributed to increased risk.

Discussion: Research on perinatal suicidality emphasizes psychosocial risk factors, while cognitive aspects remain underexplored. It is important to assess suicidality in pregnant women independently of depression, as many women with suicidal ideation (SI) do not have depression or anxiety. The transition from SI to action remains complex, requiring further research. Limitations in current studies include cross-sectional designs and suboptimal measurement tools.

Conclusion: Depression, anxiety, relationship status, IPV and socioeconomic status are risk factors for perinatal suicidality. Further research is needed to explore the transition from SI to action, improving screening tools, evaluating screening effectiveness during pregnancy, and exploring risk factors for specific groups such as women with a diagnosis of HIV.

KEYWORDS: Pregnancy, Perinatal, Postpartum, Suicide, Suicidal ideation, Suicidal behaviours, Risk factors, Predictors

1. INTRODUCTION:

The perinatal period, encompassing pregnancy, childbirth, and the first year postpartum (1) is a public health priority (2). In 2020, approximately 287,000 maternal deaths occurred worldwide (3). In the UK, the 2020-2022 MBRRACE-UK report revealed suicide and sepsis being the most prevalent direct causes for maternal deaths, accounting for 0.89 deaths per 100,000 women (4). Suicide has become a significant factor in maternal mortality (5).

Suicidality, as defined by the American Psychological Association, encompasses suicidal thoughts, plans, or attempts (6). Previously, pregnancy was thought to protect against suicide, but recent evidence challenges this belief (7-9). In high-income countries, suicide is a leading cause of death within the first year postpartum, with Italy reporting 2.30 maternal suicides per 100,000 live births (10). MBRRACE-UK data revealed maternal suicide risk tripled in 2020 compared to 2017–2019 (11). However, the situation is even more critical in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where maternal suicide accounts for approximately 1% of pregnancy-related deaths with regional prevalence ranging from 0.65% in Africa to 3.55% in the Eastern Mediterranean (12).

Maternal suicidality impacts families and communities, increasing cognitive and developmental risks in children (7, 13), low birth weight in infants (14), and suicidal ideation (SI) in children of depressed mothers. (15). Despite recent progress, research on maternal suicidality remains fragmented (14), with most studies emerging in the last five years (16). Risk factors for maternal suicidality include depression, past suicide

attempts, and low income (14, 17, 18). Existing studies only partially explain complex factors involved (14) with further exploration needed on socio-economic influences such as employment, social support, and access to mental health services.

Although reviews on suicidality prevalence exist (19, 20), to my knowledge, only one systematic review explores risk factors (14). Most articles in this review lacked methodological rigor, highlighting the need for more robust research. This study aims to address the following research question:

"What risk factors are associated with suicidality in the perinatal period?"

2. METHODS:

A systematic review (SR) design was undertaken following Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines (21). SR can inform future research, clinical practices, and policy by synthesising existing evidence (22).

2.1. Search Strategy

Framework

The SPiDER framework (Sample, Phenomenon of Interest, Design, Evaluation, Research type) (23) was used to develop search strategy. SPiDER is an appropriate tool for reviews that expect to include qualitative research (24) rather than solely quantifiable data (25).

Databases

Peer-reviewed articles were searched across three databases: (i) PubMed, which includes biomedical research, indexed with medical subject headings (26); (ii) CINAHL, which focuses on nursing and allied health (27); and (iii) EBSCO's Psychology and Behavioral Sciences Collection, which focuses on mental processes and behaviour (28).

Keywords

Keywords were selected based on relevance to the research topic and combined using appropriate BOOLEAN operators such as AND, OR, NOT. Variation of terms were captured using quotation marks, and wildcard asterisks (*). All keywords were adapted for each database ([Supplementary Materials 1](#)).

Key search terms included:

- Pregnancy-related terms (e.g., "Pregnancy", "Perinatal", "Postpartum")
- Suicidality-related terms (e.g., "Suicide", "Suicidal ideation", "Suicidal behaviours")
- Risk-related terms (e.g., "Risk factors", "Predictors")

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

Using the SPIDER tool, the review focused on (Table 1):

- Sample: Perinatal women (pregnant women and new mothers up to one year postpartum).
- Phenomenon of Interest: Suicidality, including SI, attempts, and completed suicide.
- Design: Quantitative (cross-sectional, cohort, case-control studies, surveys), qualitative (interviews, focus groups), and mixed-methods studies.
- Evaluation: Studies identifying risk factors or correlates of suicidality.
- Research Type: Original research articles with primary data collection.
- The review focused on up-to-date data by including papers from the past six years from 2018 to 2024.
- Articles published in English.

Exclusion Criteria

- Non-pregnant women or beyond one-year postpartum, postmenopausal women and fathers.
- Subgroup-focused studies (e.g., adolescents, HIV-positive women, veterans), as these groups may have unique risk factors that are not applicable to the general perinatal population.

- SR, meta-analyses, literature reviews, abstracts and conference proceedings.
- Studies focusing on self-harm or other psychiatric conditions.

Table 1: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

SPiDER	Include	Exclude
Sample	Perinatal women, Aged 18 years and above	Non-pregnant women, Beyond one year postpartum, Studies focusing on fathers or other family members, postmenopausal women
Phenomenon of Interest	Suicidality linked to perinatal women	Studies that focus on self-harm or other mental/psychiatric or physical conditions
Design	Quantitative studies, Qualitative studies, Mixed-methods studies	Systematic review, meta- analysis, literature review
Evaluation	Studies that identify risk factors, predictors, or correlates of suicidality	General overview
Research Type	Original research articles	n/a

Table legend: The table outlines the criteria used in the review to select studies on suicidality among perinatal women, including sample population, phenomenon of interest, study design, evaluation, and research type. Studies were restricted to those published in English between 2018 and 2024. Exclusion criteria are also highlighted, including non-perinatal populations, subgroup-specific studies, and non-original research articles.

Study Screening

All search results were uploaded into EndNote reference manager (Version 21, www.clarivate.com). Duplicates were removed. The screening process comprised two phases. Phase 1 excluded ineligible articles by reviewing titles and abstracts. Phase 2 involved review of full text. Articles not meeting each of the eligibility criteria were excluded. Two authors (MS and LM) independently screened articles. The reasons for exclusion in phase 2 were recorded. Disagreements for any article were discussed between reviewers until a consensus was reached.

2.2. Data Extraction and Quality Appraisal

Data extraction included author, year, country, aim, design, method, instruments and findings. Only risk factors reported by at least two different studies were included in the review, enhancing the consistency and generalizability of the results.

Study quality was assessed using quality-adapted checklists from the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (29) and Joanna Briggs Institute (30). Article quality was categorized as poor, moderate, or high.

2.3. Data Analysis

A narrative synthesis was conducted. Narrative synthesis is useful in SRs to integrate findings from multiple studies, particularly when quantitative synthesis (such as meta-analysis) is not appropriate (31). It ensures that valuable context-specific qualitative insights are integrated, enhancing the understanding of research findings (32).

3. RESULTS:

3.1. Search Results

An initial search of electronic databases yielded 61 articles (Fig.1). After removing 19 duplicates, 42 records were screened. Seventeen records were excluded based on abstract and title screening (Phase 1). Twenty-five articles were reviewed in full text (Phase 2). Seven were excluded for reasons, including findings beyond 1 year postpartum, focus on COVID-19, specific groups, or irrelevant findings. Thus, 18 articles were included in the review.

Figure 1: PRISMA flow diagram

3.2. Summary Of Studies

a) Quality Assessment

Four articles were categorized as moderate quality, one as low quality, and thirteen as high quality. All studies were included in the final synthesis ([see Table 2](#)).

b) Study And Participants Characteristics

The eighteen studies included in this review, published between 2018 and 2024, were conducted across ten countries. The study designs comprised four prospective cohort studies, six retrospective cohort studies (with Weng et al. (33) using a nested case-control design and Yu et al. (34) employing a matched cohort design), and eight observational cross-sectional studies (Table 2). Sample sizes ranged from 100 to 5,688 for cross-sectional studies, 276 to 1,795 for prospective cohort studies, and 706 to 1,992,422 for retrospective cohort studies. Participants' mean age ranged from 25 to 33 years, and all were either pregnant or within one year postpartum. All studies focused on exposures and outcomes during pregnancy or the first year postpartum, except Yu et al. (34) which examined both short- and long-term outcomes up to 18 years. Only the short-term outcomes from Yu et al. (34) were included in this review.

c) Aspect Of Suicidality

Studies reported on various aspects of suicidality: eleven studies concentrated on SI, with Nayak and Nachane (35) also addressing postnatal depression severity alongside ideation. Four studies investigated suicide attempts and completed suicides, while three

studies encompassed suicidal behaviours collectively, including ideation, planning, and attempts (see Table 3).

d) Measurement Instruments

Measurement instruments varied across the studies. The most frequently used tools included the Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS) (n=5), International Classification of Diseases (ICD-9/10) codes (n=4), and the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9) (n=4).

Three studies (36-38) employed the WHO Composite International Diagnostic Interview (CIDI). One (39) used the revised Suicidal Behavior Questionnaire (SBQ-R). One (40) employed the Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI) for suicide risk assessment (Table 2). For the covariates, a variety of tools were used.

Table 3: Aspect of Suicidality Investigated (lead author and year of publication)

	IDEATION	ATTEMPTS & COMPLETED	BEHAVIOURS
1.	Schafer, 2024	Weng, 2018	Molla, 2022
2.	Kubota, 2020	Yu, 2024	Levey, 2019
3.	Gelabert, 2020	Yoon, 2024	de Avila Quevedo, 2021
4.	Xiao, 2023	Akaishi, 2023	
5.	Faisal-Cury, 2022		
6.	Chen, 2023		
7.	Zhang, 2022		
8.	Bete, 2024		
9.	Anbesaw, 2021		
10	Legazpi, 222		
11	Nayak, 2020		

Table legend: Out of the 18 studies, eleven focused on suicidal ideation. Four studies examined suicide attempts and completed suicides, while three studies covered all types of suicidal behaviors, including thoughts, planning, and attempts.

3.3. Summary Of Findings

a) **DEPRESSION**

Thirteen studies identified depression as significant predictor of suicidality during the perinatal period. Yu et al. (34) found that women with perinatal depression had threefold increased likelihood of suicidal behaviour compared to unaffected women with rates of 5.62 versus 1.01 occurrences per 1000 person-years. Faisal-Cury et al. (41) reported that antenatal depression severity was associated with SI, with 2.6% of mildly depressed and 17.5% of moderately depressed pregnant women reporting ideation.

Studies from Ethiopia (36, 37) found prenatal depressive symptoms increased the risk of SI by 2.79 to 4 times in pregnant women. Zhang et al. (42) also found a strong association between third trimester depression and SI with odds ratio (OR) of 8.231. However, these studies did not differentiate between current and previous depression. Legazpi et al. (43) reported that a history of depression raised prenatal SI risk with a regression coefficient of 0.120, while Kubota et al. (44) found severe depressive symptoms and a history of major depressive disorder were significant risk factors for perinatal SI with ORs of 1.25 and 2.16 respectively.

Yu et al. (34) also noted that a history of depression increased the risk of suicidal behaviour, though not as strongly as postnatal depression. The postpartum period was significantly associated with SI, with Nayak and Nachane (35) finding that 31% of depressed women experienced SI at six weeks postpartum. Chen et al. (45) found postpartum SI was 16 times higher in women with depression than those without (51.8% vs. 3.3%). Gelabert et al. (46) confirmed a strong link between postpartum depression and SI, with 81%–86% of mothers experiencing both. At eight weeks, 62.1% of these mothers had severe postpartum depression, rising to 70% by thirty-two weeks.

de Avila Quevedo et al. (40) found that postpartum suicide risk was associated with chronic mood disorders, with mothers having exclusive depressive episodes facing a 6.50 times higher risk and those with mixed episodes (mothers who exhibited both manic or hypomanic symptoms alongside depressive symptoms) facing a 41.50 times higher risk. Pregnancy was a high-risk period for both ideation and attempts. Molla, Nigussie, and Girma (39) reported 2.32 times higher odds of suicidal behaviour in depressed pregnant

women. Akaishi et al. (47) and Yu et al. (34) highlighted prenatal and postpartum depression as significant risk factors for suicide attempts and completions, with postnatal depression showing a stronger association.

b) ANXIETY

Eight studies highlighted anxiety disorders as significant factors for suicidality, particularly postpartum. Anxiety contributed to suicide attempts within one year postpartum (47). Schafer et al. (48) found that prenatal anxiety was a stronger predictor of postpartum SI (OR=1.185) compared to prenatal depression (OR=1.018) and prenatal ideation (OR=1.58). This is the only study suggesting anxiety might be a stronger predictor than depression.

Xiao et al. (49) linked early pregnancy anxiety to a "persistent high levels" trajectory of SI. Contrary to other studies, Chen et al. (45) reported anxiety as a protective factor against SI in women with depression.

de Avila Quevedo et al. (40) reported a 3.69-fold increase in postpartum suicide risk in mothers with anxiety disorders. Zhang et al. (42) found prenatal and attachment anxiety increases odds of SI, with ORs of 3.420 and 2.015, respectively. Bete et al. (37) and Anbesaw et al. (36) found a 3.37-fold and three-fold increased risk of SI, respectively, in pregnant women with anxiety symptoms.

c) FETAL LOSS

Three studies identified fetal loss as a risk factor for suicidality during the perinatal period. Anbesaw et al. (36) and Legazpi et al. (43) found that women with a history of fetal loss were 2.45 times more likely to experience SI compared to their counterparts.

In the postnatal period, Weng et al. (33) reported higher rates of completed and attempted suicides among mothers experiencing fetal loss. Stillbirths, miscarriages (accidental), and pregnancy terminations (intentional) were linked to 5.2, 3.81-, and 3.12-times higher rates of completed suicide, respectively. For attempted suicides, the odds were 2.5 times and 2.1 times higher for miscarriages and pregnancy terminations respectively.

d) MARITAL STATUS

Eight studies have highlighted marital status as a significant factor in perinatal suicidality. Zhang et al. (42) found that marital satisfaction reduced SI (OR=0.277), while being single increased the risk. Molla, Nigussie, and Girma (39) reported that single respondents were 5.69 times more likely to engage in suicidal behavior. Levey et al. (38) also found higher odds of planning and attempting suicide among unmarried individuals with ORs of 1.53 and 1.66, respectively.

Anbesaw et al. (36) and Faisal-Cury et al. (41) found single, widowed, or divorced individuals had 2.8 (36) times greater risk of SI during pregnancy. Conversely, de Avila Quevedo et al. (40) found no link to cohabitation but noted that partners' mood episodes, such as episodes of depression or mania, were linked to higher suicide risk, though this disappeared after adjusting for confounding factors. Yu et al. (34) and Chen et al. (45)

found that living alone was associated with a higher risk of perinatal depression with OR of 2.861 (45).

e) ABUSE

Intimate partner violence:

Five studies found that intimate partner violence (IPV) was a significant predictor of perinatal suicidality. Levey et al (38) reported that IPV increased the risk of SI by 1.81 times, planning by 2.21 times, and attempts by 2.11 times in pregnant women. Similarly, Molla, Nigussie, and Girma (39) reported that IPV increased suicidal behaviour risk by 7.60 times in pregnant women. Anbesaw et al. (36) and Bete et al. (37) also found that IPV was associated with a 2.43 to 3.46 times higher risk of SI during pregnancy. Additionally, Chen et al. (45) identified IPV as an independent predictor of postpartum SI, with and without depression, with ORs of 1.153 versus 1.576.

Childhood abuse

Childhood abuse is a strong predictor of perinatal suicidality. Chen et al. (45) found negative childhood experiences predicted SI in postpartum women. Levey et al. (38) reported that childhood abuse increased the risk of SI by 2.57 times, planning by 3 times, and attempts by 2.43 times in pregnant women.

f) SUBSTANCE USE

Yu et al. (34) found poisoning was the most common suicide method among postpartum women with depression. Yoon et al. (50) reported opioid overdose in 79% of postpartum suicide attempts. 0.3% of women with opioid use disorder had increased postpartum suicide attempts. Heavy smoking and alcohol use disorder significantly raised postpartum suicide attempts, with ORs of 23.09 and 163.54, respectively (47). However, de Avila Quevedo et al. (40) found no significant link between alcohol addiction and suicide risk.

g) OTHER FACTORS IDENTIFIED

Primiparous

Primiparity, or first childbirth, is linked to increased suicidality. Chen et al. (45) found higher SI in primiparous postpartum women without depression with OR of 1.476. Yu et al. (34) found primiparity more common in women with perinatal depression. However, de Avila Quevedo et al. (40) noted that this association disappeared after adjusting for confounding factors.

Younger age

Akaishi et al. (47) found lower age distribution among women attempting prepartum and postpartum suicide with adjusted OR of 0.99 and 0.96. Faisal-Cury et al. (41) observed a higher incidence of SI in women aged 15-19, while older women had lower risks.

Education and Socioeconomic Status

Lower socioeconomic status and education levels are both linked to higher suicidality. Yu et al. (34) and Faisal-Cury et al. (41) reported that women with lower education had higher SI, though this correlation weakened after logistic regression. Conversely, Kubota et al. (44) found that higher educational attainment increased SI risk (OR 1.19). Socioeconomic status also plays a role, with lower household income and unemployment associated with higher antenatal SI risk (41, 43). However, these associations diminished after adjusting for confounders (34, 45).

BMI

There were mixed findings regarding Body mass index (BMI) and suicidality. Yu et al. (34) found women with perinatal depression often had higher BMIs, while Nayak and Nachane (35) reported a negative association between waist-to-hip ratio (WHR) and suicidality with correlation coefficient of -0.36. BMI, height, and weight showed no significant correlation.

Sleep Quality

Two studies reported that poor sleep quality increased suicidality. Akaishi et al. (47) found that insomnia raised postpartum suicide attempt odds (OR=3.17). Anbesaw et al. (36) also noted a 2.85 times higher SI risk in women with poor sleep quality.

Stress and Health

Stress and poor health significantly elevate perinatal suicidality (37, 41, 45). Stressful life events, like financial or marital issues, increase SI (OR=1.88) (43, 46). Pregnant women with stress had 2.50 times higher odds of SI (36). Poor health, including chronic illness, raises suicide risk by 4.47 to 11.7 times (39).

Personality Dimensions

Gelabert et al. (46) found higher neuroticism and psychoticism increased postpartum SI risk (OR=1.03 each), while extraversion was negatively associated. Xiao et al. (49) reported lower neuroticism protected against persistent high level of SI (OR=0.836).

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Major Findings of The Review

This systematic review of 18 studies identified key risk factors for perinatal suicidality, including depression, IPV, anxiety, being unmarried, fetal loss, childhood abuse, and substance use. It also highlighted the impact of a vulnerable psychosocial profile, characterized by lower education and socioeconomic status, younger age, primiparity, poor sleep, stress, poor health, and certain personality traits. This review aligns with previous findings by Legazpi et al. (14), which also noted major depressive disorder, anxiety, and other factors as risks. However, Legazpi's review identified multiparity as a risk factor based on one South African study, whereas the current review found primiparity to be a risk factor across three international studies.

4.2. Risk Factors of Suicidality

Most research focused on psychosocial risk factors such as mental disorders, experiences of abuse, and sociocultural factors, with only one study (45) examining cognitive aspects. This is likely due to the complexity of measuring cognitive and personality factors versus simpler psychosocial variables. Cognitive factors, such as impaired decision-making, feelings of worthlessness, and guilt, predispose individuals to suicidality (16) and these need to be explored further to fully understand why suicidality was found to be more common in late pregnancy (39, 44, 49) and even more frequent during the one-year postpartum period (50).

Women with current or past depression had 2.16 to 16 times greater risk of suicidality, with a stronger association for current depression and postnatal depression. The intensity of depression positively correlated with increased suicidality risk, supporting broader findings in the general population that depression is a major condition linked to suicide (51-53).

The US Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) recommends screening for depression in perinatal populations (54), reflecting its significant role in suicidality. The Integrated Motivational-Volitional (IMV) model of suicidal behavior describes depression-related suicidality as "arrested flight," where defeat and entrapment create conditions conducive to suicide behavior (55). Depression also lowers serotonin levels, contributing to suicidality (56), and involves complex pathways including neurotransmitter systems, stressors, and others (57).

This review found peripartum women with anxiety had a 3-4 times higher risk of suicidality. Substance use (opioids, alcohol, tobacco) significantly increased this risk. Combined factors such as anxiety and substance use further elevated suicide risk in people with depression (51). This suggests that anxiety and substance use may influence suicidality as factors associated with depression. Notably, trait anxiety predicted SI throughout the perinatal period, with two-thirds of postpartum women showing both anxiety symptoms and SI, exacerbated by the stress of adjusting to motherhood (58).

This review found IPV, and history of childhood abuse predisposed women to suicidality during the perinatal period, with IPV increasing risk by 1.81 to 7.60 times. IPV includes physical, sexual, emotional, psychological, or economic forms of abuse (59). Pregnancy is a high-risk time for IPV, with many women reporting that they encountered IPV for the first time during pregnancy (60). The prevalence of IPV during pregnancy ranges from 4% to 20% (61), and it may increase following childbirth. Research shows that the percentage of young mothers reporting IPV rose from 17.9% at 6 months postpartum to 25.3% at 12 months postpartum, with 33.8% of women experiencing some form of IPV at either 6 or 12 months postpartum (62).

Additionally, physical aggression may intensify during pregnancy or the postpartum period. Women who had experienced IPV from their current partner in the previous six months were 2.7 times more likely to experience IPV again throughout their pregnancy and for up to six months postpartum compared to women who had never experienced IPV (63). A systematic review on maternal suicidality found that physical abuse had a strong correlation with suicide behavior (16), while another study identified that emotional

abuse from a partner had high impact on suicidality (64). IPV is also a key driver of suicidality in the general population, where IPV accounted for 6.1% of homicide-suicide events and 4.5% of single suicides (65).

Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs), such as childhood abuse, neglect, and household difficulties, are linked to a heightened risk of depression, early death and suicidality (66-68). Additionally, ACEs significantly increase the odds of suicide attempts by two to five times (69). Notably, women tend to have higher ACE scores than men (70), and maternal ACEs have been associated with disrupted cortisol patterns during pregnancy (71), emphasizing the need for more research on how ACEs affect maternal health.

Previous and current fetal loss, including abortion, stillbirth, and miscarriage, increases perinatal suicidality risk by 2.1 to 5.2 times. Fetal loss can induce hopelessness and defeat, key factors in suicidality according to IMV model (72).

Unmarried women have 1.53 to 5.69 times higher odds of suicidality than married women either directly or indirectly through depression. Marital contentment, however, provides protection. This may be due to a perceived lack of social and emotional support, leading to feelings of isolation, and helplessness during pregnancy (73). A Norwegian study found that in the general population, widowed, separated, divorced, or never-married individuals faced higher suicide risk compared to married individuals. Separated individuals faced over six times the risk, particularly within 30 days post-separation (74).

This review highlights the need to address prenatal psychiatric issues beyond depression, as not all pregnant women with suicidality present with depression. A study found that 67% of pregnant women with SI did not have major depression, 65% did not have anxiety, and 54% had neither condition (73). This identifies the importance of assessing other risk factors identified in this review to avoid under-identification.

In the general population, anxiety, alcohol use, opioid use disorders, marital status, and depression are known suicide risk factors (53, 74-77). These risks are equally relevant for pregnant women, who are more likely to experience SI (18). Future research should focus on novel suicide risk assessment techniques, weighing the benefits and risks of screening during pregnancy (54, 78).

Addressing suicidality is challenging for medical professionals and policymakers, particularly in predicting who will act on SI. The ideation-to-action concept distinguishes SI from attempts, with different causes and predictors (78). While ideation is linked to despair, depression, and mental illnesses, it is complex to predict when SI will progress to suicidal action (78, 79). The IMV model explains this transition in three phases. The *pre-motivational* phase examines background factors that trigger ideation, the *motivational* phase examines ideation development via feelings of defeat and entrapment, and the *volitional* phase examines transition to action via factors like access to resources, impulsivity, and planning (55, 72). Despite these frameworks, no single approach fully distinguishes between SI and action (55). Continued refinement of these models and the development of new strategies are crucial for improving prevention and intervention efforts.

The WHO guide for integrating perinatal mental health into maternal and child health services recommends a stepped-care approach, offering basic interventions broadly and reserves intensive care for those with higher needs (80). It focuses on mental health services for vulnerable groups such as individuals with a history of mental health disorders, substance abuse, physical illness, self-harm, infant loss, and exposure to violence. Notably, the current review highlights that unmarried women are 1.53 to 5.69 times more likely to experience suicidal behavior than married women—a significant finding not included in the WHO guidelines. This new evidence could inform future revisions and updates to the guidelines.

4.3. Limitations Of the Included Studies

The studies in this review have several limitations. Cross-sectional designs, used by eight studies, restrict the ability to establish temporal causality between suicidality and variables, such as depression, anxiety, or substance use. This design can only identify associations, making it unclear whether changes in these variables precede or follow SI. Additionally, reliance on a single question within PHQ-9 or EPDS in several studies reduces statistical power and complicates the interpretation of suicidality. The ambiguity of the EPDS self-harm single question adds further complexity, as it can encompass various behaviors beyond SI (81).

Furthermore, the EPDS and PHQ-9 were primarily designed for depression screening and may not effectively capture suicidality (18, 82, 83). While suicidality often coexists with depression, some pregnant women with suicidality may not be depressed (73), suggesting these tools may miss non-depressed individuals at risk of suicide. Single-item

measures are also unreliable predictors of future SI (84). The reliance on self-reported data introduces recall biases, and seven studies using datasets, may not have captured cases where individuals were stopped from self-harm or had minor injuries that did not require medical treatment.

4.4. Strengths and Limitations of This Review

This review demonstrates notable strengths, including adherence to PRISMA guidelines for transparency and a focus of current insights from the past six years. The involvement of a second reviewer minimized selection bias, and the inclusion of diverse samples from various income countries enhanced relevance. The review effectively identifies key perinatal mental health risk factors, informing targeted interventions and professional training.

However, the review also has limitations. The use of narrative synthesis, due to study design heterogeneity, limited the ability to conduct a meta-analysis. Second, it broadly identified suicidality risk factors without differentiating between ideation, planning, and attempts, potentially overlooking important nuances. Third, factors reported by single studies were intentionally excluded for consistency. Fourth, specific populations, such as veterans and HIV-positive women were not included, possibly missing relevant risk factors. Despite these issues, the review offers valuable insights into perinatal suicidality.

5. CONCLUSION:

This systematic review of 18 studies identified risk factors associated with suicidality in the perinatal period including depression, anxiety, IPV, being unmarried, fetal loss, childhood abuse, and substance use. Additionally, a vulnerable psychosocial profile—marked by lower education, lower socioeconomic status, younger age, primiparity, poor sleep, stress, poor health, and specific personality traits—was also linked to increased risk. For future research, advancing the understanding of perinatal suicidality requires addressing several research priorities:

1. Identifying factors that lead from SI to actions is crucial, as ideation is common during pregnancy. Understanding this transition will improve prevention strategies.
2. Evaluate the accuracy of single-question suicide screening within depression screening tools. Alternatively, future research should focus on creating measures specifically designed to assess suicidality in the perinatal period, ensuring they reflect the complexities of this period.
3. To better understand the causality of suicidality, more longitudinal studies are needed. These studies should track the development of suicidality, providing insights into the causes and triggers over time.
4. It is essential to evaluate all groups of perinatal women, including veterans or HIV-positive, to ensure that risk factors applicable to these populations are identified.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

1. WHO: World Health Organization
2. SI: Suicidal ideation
3. LMIC: Low- and middle-income countries
4. SR: Systematic review
5. PRISMA: Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
6. SPiDER: Sample, Phenomenon of Interest, Design, Evaluation, Research type
7. EPDS: Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale
8. ICD: International Classification of Diseases
9. PHQ: Patient Health Questionnaire
10. CIDI: WHO Composite International Diagnostic Interview
11. SBQ-R: revised Suicidal Behavior Questionnaire
12. MINI: Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview
13. OR: Odds ratio
14. IPV: Intimate partner violence
15. BMI: Body mass index
16. IMV: Integrated Motivational-Volitional

DECLARATION

- **Ethics approval and consent to participate:** Not applicable
- **Consent for publication:** Not applicable
- **Availability of data and materials:** All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this published article.
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- **Authors' contributions:** MS had full access to all the data in the study and takes responsibility for its integrity and accuracy. She was responsible for the concept, design, data analysis, drafting, and leading of the manuscript.

LM guided development of the search strategy, contributed to screening and analyses, and supported revisions of the final manuscript.
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Table 2: Table of Characteristics of the Included Studies

First author, year, country	Aim of study	Participants	Design	Measurement Instruments	Risk factors	Study Quality
Schafer, 2024, USA	To investigate the relative contribution of antenatal anxiety symptoms, depression symptoms, and SI towards postpartum SI	N=276	Prospective cohort study	PHQ-9	Antenatal anxiety is a stronger predictor	Medium
Weng, 2018, Taiwan	To investigate whether stillbirth, miscarriage, or termination of pregnancy increase the risks of attempted and completed suicide within a year postnatally	N= 1,992,422	Nested case-control study	ICD-9-CM codes	Fetal loss	High
Nayak, 2020, India	To assess the efficacy of anthropometric determinants as risk markers of severity of postnatal depression and SI postnatally	N=100	Cross-sectional study	EPDS	Waist-to-hip ratio (WHR)	Poor
Yu, 2024, Sweden	To examine the association between PND and risk of short- and long-term suicidal behavior	N= 952 061	Matched Cohort study	ICD-10 codes	Depression, Postnatal depression has a greater association than antenatal depression	High
Yoon, 2024, USA	To examine the association between prenatal OUD and postpartum suicide attempts, particularly those involving opioid poisoning	N= 61,481	Retrospective cohort study	ICD 9/10-CM codes	Prenatal OUD diagnosis	High
Molla, 2022, Ethiopia	To assess the prevalence and associated factors of suicidal behavior among pregnant mothers in Southern Ethiopia	N= 504	Cross-sectional design	SBQ-R	Depression, Intimate partner violence, Being unmarried, Gestation age greater than 27 weeks,	High

					Chronic medical illness	
Faisal-Cury, 2022, Brazil	To estimate the prevalence of SI during pregnancy and its association with antenatal depression (AD) and sociodemographic factors in a LMIC	N= 769	Retrospective Cohort study	PHQ-9	Depression, Sociodemographic vulnerability	High
Chen, 2023, Japan	To separately examine the prevalence and risk factors of SI in postpartum women with and without depression	N= 5688	Cross-sectional design	EPDS	Depression, Psychosocial variables	High
Zhang, 2022, China	To investigate the prevalence of SI in the third trimester and associated predictors including psychological factors such as attachment	N= 432	Cross-sectional study	EPDS	Poor marital satisfaction, High attachment anxiety, Prenatal depression, Prenatal anxiety	Medium
Akaishi, 2023, Japan	To identify the demographic characteristics and predisposing risks for peripartum suicide attempts	N=804 617	Cohort study used retrospective data	ICD-10 codes	Depression, Younger age, Prenatal history of alcohol use disorder, Anxiety disorders, Personality disorder, Schizophrenia, Heavy smoking	High
Kubota, 2020, Japan	To investigate the risk factors for SI among perinatal women in Japan	N= 430	Prospective cohort study	EPDS	Higher education, Early severe depressive symptoms, A history of MDD, Mental disease	High

Gelabert, 2020, Spain	To investigate the role of personality dimensions, depressive symptoms, and other psychosocial variables in predicting postpartum SI	N=1795	Prospective cohort study	EPDS	High neuroticism, psychoticism, Early depressive symptoms, Psychiatric history, Stressful events during pregnancy	Medium
Bete, 2024, Ethiopia	To assess the magnitude and factors associated with SI in pregnant women	N=543	Cross-sectional study	CIDI	Depressive symptoms, Anxiety symptoms, Intimate partner violence, Stress, Unwanted pregnancy, Hyperemesis gravidarum	High
Anbesaw, 2021, Ethiopia	To explore the prevalence of SI and associated factors among pregnant women attending antenatal care in Jimma, Ethiopia	N=415	Cross-sectional study	CIDI	Depression, Anxiety, Intimate partner violence, Lack of cohabiting partners, Previous history of abortion, Poor sleep quality, Stress	High
Legazpi, 2022, Spain	To determine the prevalence and risk factors of SI during pregnancy among Spanish-speaking women	N= 1524	Cross-sectional design	PHQ-9	History of depression, Previous abortion, Unemployment, Immigration status,	High

					Stressors like financial and marital problems	
De Avila Quevedo, 2021, Brazil	To assess the suicide risk in women who experienced depressive or mixed episodes of mood change during the postpartum period and to determine which disorder is more related to suicide risk in the same period	N= 706	Retrospective cohort study	MINI	Anxiety disorders, Various types of mood episodes	High
Levey, 2019, Peru	To characterize suicidal behavior among cohort of pregnant Peruvian women and identify risk factors for transitions between behaviors	N= 2062	Cross-sectional design	CIDI	Childhood abuse, Intimate partner violence	High
Xiao, 2023, China	To investigate the prevalence of SI from early pregnancy to six weeks postpartum, and further explore the trajectories of perinatal SI and their risk factors	N= 629	Prospective longitudinal cohort study	PHQ-9	Anxiety symptoms during early pregnancy, Neuroticism	Medium

Table legend: This table includes the data extracted from included studies: author, year, country, aim, participants, design, instruments, key findings and study quality.

Table abbreviations:

SI: Suicidal Ideation

PHQ-9: Patient Health Questionnaire

EPDS: Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale

PND: Perinatal Depression

ICD: International Classification of Diseases

OD: Opioid Use Disorder

SBQ-R: Revised Suicidal Behaviour Questionnaire

LMIC: Low- And Middle-Income Countries

AD= Antenatal Depression

CIDI: Composite international diagnostic interview

MINI: Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview

MDD: Major Depressive Disorder

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

SUPPLEMENTARY
MATERIAL 1.docx

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